

ABSTRACT

Building scalable businesses that last is the trend nowadays. Many Filipino student entrepreneurs with the skills to promote their business online and on-site have become an upward-moving trend contributing to the Philippine economic growth. However, student entrepreneurs usually feel anxious about putting up a business and making it large as they normally lack entrepreneurial leadership and management capabilities. This study explored the impact of business simulation among Accountancy Business and Management (ABM) learners through the Studentpreneur Program. The program was designed to teach student entrepreneurs how to make and manage their organization, develop and plan innovative business enterprises, create company brand logos, and make their business advertisements. Qualitative and quantitative data were used in this study to determine the level of business strategy skills of ABM learners. Data Analysis revealed that the Business Enterprise Simulation fostered student entrepreneurs' business strategy skills, indicating a high rating level. The t-test concluded that there was a statistically significant improvement in the business strategy skills of the participants. The study exposed important knowledge associated with business while doing simulation-based learning. The findings indicated that the program has enriched participants in business development and marketing, strategic planning, problem-solving, communication, and leadership skills.

Keywords: *Student entrepreneurs, business simulation, strategy skills, ABM learners, business enterprise*

INTRODUCTION

This paper explored the impact of business simulation among Accountancy Business and Management (ABM) learners through the Studentpreneur Program. The program was designed to teach student entrepreneurs how to make and manage their organization, develop and plan innovative business enterprises, create company brand logos, and make their business advertisements. Becoming a good entrepreneur requires various skills, including but not limited to financial management, marketing, sales, leadership, and problem-solving. The Studentpreneur Program is designed to teach student entrepreneurs these skills and more, providing them with a solid foundation to build their businesses and succeed in the competitive world of entrepreneurship. Through the program, students learn how to identify market opportunities, create effective business plans, manage finances, and develop marketing strategies that can help them reach their target audience. Additionally, the program emphasizes the importance of leadership and teamwork, teaching students how to work effectively with others to achieve common goals. Overall, the Studentpreneur Program provides a comprehensive education in entrepreneurship that can help students develop the skills they need to succeed in any business venture.

Business simulations are innovative instruction models for active or cooperative learning. Researchers have identified that all students enrolled in courses that use business simulations as a teaching tool become actively engaged in the learning activities, particularly when the academic instructor provides guidance and feedback regularly throughout the study period (Levant et al., 2016). Moreover, Salas, Wildman, and Piccalo (2009) define business simulations as 'any artificial or synthetic environment created to manage an individual's (or team's) experiences with reality.'

Business simulations provide opportunities for the 'active construction of meaning and knowledge' through pedagogies such as experiential, discovery, and constructivist learning (Levant, Coulmont & Sandu, 2016, p. 371). Experiential learning is evidenced through the students engaging directly with the simulation providing experience dealing with the consequences of the decisions they implement. Discovery learning is successful when students act on previous knowledge to discover new meanings of the concepts they have studied. Dellaportas and Hassall (2013) reinforce this by identifying that knowledge creation from experiencing an actual or simulated environment is based on constructing realistic meaning for the learner.

Digital simulations have become widespread in higher education using authentic learning environments and assessments. These digital simulations have become dynamic tools that represent actions and roles from the students' future fields of employment, allowing the students to engage in the 'interactive, authentic and self-driven acquisition of knowledge' (Vlachopoulos & Makri, 2017, p. 4). In addition, it has been shown through student feedback, as well as pre-and post-simulation testing, that

simulations assist students in the development of 'soft' or 'enterprise' skills (Morin, Tamberelli & Buhagiar (2019).

Despite the growing interest in using simulations in different fields, several gaps in the existing research on business enterprise simulations warrant further investigation. Despite the positive feedback on simulations in business, there is still a need to explore the underlying cause of its impact on student entrepreneurs. Investigating the role of simulation in fostering business-related skills can shed light on generalizing results and may help develop Business Enterprise Program that is beneficial among young entrepreneurs.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. This study used the descriptive research design to determine the impact of Business Enterprise Simulation in Fostering Business Strategy Skills among student entrepreneurs. Rillo and Alieto (2018) defined descriptive research as a purposive process of gathering, analyzing, classifying, and tabulating data about prevailing conditions, practices, procedures, trends, and cause-effect relationships and then making an adequate and accurate interpretation of such data with or without or sometimes minimal aid of statistical methods. Also, this method ascertains prevailing conditions of facts in a group under study that gives either qualitative or quantitative, or both, descriptions of the general characteristics of the group as results.

Participants/Respondents. The study participants were the 33 entrepreneur students enrolled in the Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM) Strand in Senior High School. The participants undertook the Studentpreneur Program. The participants were randomly divided into six (6) teams and received orientations, lectures, and technical workshops addressing aspects of business organizations. Each team organized its management and strategy schemes and decided on what product they wanted to pursue and develop. After weeks of training about product development, each team showcased their Product Prototype and presented their advertisement. Participants also worked hard on other aspects of the business-like price policy and sales team management as well as production management and packaging. The teacher-in-charge had to provide feedback and debrief each team after directly observing each session to improve their products. The final simulation served as the culminating phase of the program. Different teams compete with each other, and participants develop business strategy skills like critical thinking, problem-solving, and collaboration with peers.

Data Collection Procedure. The Business Strategy Skills Self-Evaluation was a researcher-made questionnaire comprising 25-item questions on a 4-point scale (scored from 1 to 4, never to always). The instrument got a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.85, indicating reliability. The questionnaire's items included strategic planning, communication skills, management, and entrepreneurial ability. The participants were asked to rate the questionnaire at the beginning and the end of the Entrepreneur Program. The difference between the two ratings indicated the level of improvement in the business strategy skills obtained after the program. In doing this, the researcher used the dependent t-test (paired-samples t-test in SPSS Statistics).

Other data sources for evaluation were based on interviews, FGD, researcher observation, lessons learned reflections of the participants, trial, and final assessment evaluation. Data Analysis was analyzed to determine the themes regarding the impact of the Studentpreneur Program. Content analysis was done to determine the themes from the student's reflection assessment of the business simulation. Content analysis is a research technique for making replicable and valid inferences from texts (or other meaningful matter) to their use contexts (Krippendorff, 2013).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As indicated in Table 1, the business strategy skills of the ABM learners before the Studentpreneur Program is *moderate*, with a mean of 58.61 and a standard deviation of 10.01. After the Program, the participants were rated 76.58 for the mean and 9.83 with a standard deviation of 9.83, obtaining a *High Level* of Business Strategy Skills.

Table 1. Shows the business strategy skills level of ABM studentpreneurs before and after the Studentpreneur Program

	n	Mean	sd	Descriptions
Before the Program	33	58.61	10.01	Moderate

After the Program 33 76.58 9.83 High

Score Range	Business Strategy Skill Rating
67-100	High Level
34-66.99	Moderate Level
1-33.99	Low Level

As shown in Table 2, the t-test resulted in $t(32)=-34.352$, $p<0.001$. Due to the means of the two ratings (before and after the Studentpreneur program) and the direction of the t-value, it was concluded that there was a statistically significant improvement in the business strategy skills of the participants from 58.61 ± 10.01 m to 76.58 ± 9.83 m ($p<0.001$); an improvement of 17.97 ± 3.0 m.

Table 2. T-test results for the difference in the level of business strategy skills among ABM studentpreneurs

	mean	sd	t	df	p-value	remarks
Before & After	-17.970	3.005	-34.352	32	< 0.001	significant

Note: * $p<0.05$, ** $p<0.001$

Impacts of Business Enterprise Simulation

After the themes have been generated, 3 main areas have been identified as key learnings from the Business Enterprise Simulation Studentpreneur Program.

Table 3. Learning Themes

Theme	Sub-theme
Business operations	Student’s decision-making effect
	Planning
	Innovative Product
	Investment and saving
Business Enterprise Skills	Strategy
	Strong Teamwork
	Individual Skills
	Time Management
Food Tasting Feedback	Product Challenges
	Product Innovation and Product Adjustment
	Packaging
	Logo enhancement
	Product Oversight

Data Analysis revealed that the Business Enterprise Simulation Studentpreneur Program improves not only the business conceptual knowledge of the participants on putting up a business but also helped them enrich their business development and marketing skills, strategic planning skills, problem-solving skills, communication, and leadership skills. Results indicated that the participants viewed the program as a success, and it has helped them better cope with teamwork challenges and improve their enterprise skills as a student.

It is interesting to note that the theme of *Business Enterprise Skills* has emphasized the ability of students to work with their peers, embrace the different challenges in the organization they are with, and acknowledge other assets of the team.

“One of our team members is excellent at doing the balance sheets and income, so she oversees our sales and income summary. I am good at marketing and production of products, so I was tasked to do it. Other members have other attributes that make the team work well. Sometimes there are challenges like making time to make our food product since we have other classes, but we take turns doing it anyway.” (Maria)

“I have a team member that seldom talks, so I assigned him to Product Packaging since he works well in that task. Those who are talkative are normally the ones that draw many customers. I believe that each member has something to share or contribute to the team.” (Jose)

Fearon et al. (2019) identified a clear link between student involvement in business simulations and the development of employability or enterprise skills coinciding with the outcomes

reported by the students from this study. This claim is further supported by the study of Ornellas, Falkner & Stalbrandt (2019), who report that authentic learning tasks and assessments enhance the development of transferrable skills.

During the Food Tasting Day, an Initial Product assessment was made, and students were given feedback on their product. Feedbacking has become a key for students to learn, reflect and enhance their products. This has made the students work together and improve a lot.

“We are given tips on improving our packaging and our product's taste. Our logo was too small, so we enhanced the color and made some icons to capture our product. The feedback allows us to decide whether to accept the revision or stick with what we believe is already good for us.” (Nerissa)

“There are some things that we do not know and have not calculated in the long run. We thank those teachers who shared their ideas with us. I guess it is really important to listen to the ideas of others.” (Lovely).

Studentpreneur Program Design

- a) Orientation of Business Enterprise Simulation
- b) Making of Company Organization Chart
- c) Product Innovation Development
- d) Company Brand Logo Creation
- e) Business Advertisement Making
- f) Prototype Evaluation
- g) BES Final Simulation
- h) Feedbacking and Self-Reflection

Sample Company Brand Logo

Sample business enterprise advertisement

CONCLUSION

The results suggest that the use of business enterprise simulation has fostered the business strategy skills of the participants from moderate to high level. The Studentpreneurs program has proven to be highly significant and was an effective learning and training tool that provided students with necessary learning in doing business. By providing students the opportunity to learn and grow, teachers in the academe can support their action-oriented as well as their trial-and-error learning through simulations.

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Declaration of Conflicting Interest. There are no conflicts concerning this research paper, authorship, and publication.

Funding. No funding from external sources, such as donations or grants, was received for conducting research, authorship, and publication of this paper.